

CAROTID ATHEROSCLEROSIS DISEASE: MODELLING AND ANALYSIS OF PLAQUE DEVELOPMENT

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Introduction

Atherosclerosis is caused by building up of plaque and its progression within arteries, due to deposits of fat, cholesterol, calcium, and other substances in the blood. Computational modelling of atherosclerosis has been performed last years, while the mechanisms of atherosclerosis have been used to provide insights for the understanding of the processes which lead to the plaque initiation and progression, as well as to predict plaque regions and mechanisms which are prone to disease progression [1, 2].

Methods

The 3D finite element model of the carotid artery was created using the patient-specific CT scan images in combination with several different software packages. The 3D blood flow was governed by the Navier-Stokes equations and continuity equation. Mass transfer within the blood lumen and through the arterial wall was coupled with the blood flow and modelled by the convection–diffusion equations. Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) transport in lumen of the vessel was described using Kedem-Katchalsky equations. The average blood properties were prescribed and the PAK software was used for the computational simulation, which calculated the velocity vector field and wall shear stress. Appropriate boundary conditions were employed, such as: prescribed blood flow at the inlet of the arterial segment and physiological resistance pressure at the arterial outlets.

Results and Discussion

The 3D blood flow was simulated together with the LDL transport through the lumen and artery wall, coupling the plaque progression in vessel wall. The quantification of the real patient-specific plaque progression is investigated. The hemodynamic parameters such as velocity vector field and wall shear stress were determined at the baseline (Fig. 1 (a)) and follow up (Fig. 1 (b)) time periods. Analyzing the shear stress distribution along the carotid artery at the baseline, the grey circle indicates the zone of a low shear stress value and greatest risk of plaque position and progression, which is confirmed after the follow up. Development of atherosclerosis leads to increasement of plaque volume and decrease of lumen diameter. It is followed by reduced blood flow through stenotic zone and higher shear stress which can be seen by comparing the velocity vector field and shear stress distribution at the baseline

and follow up. The carotid diameter is approximately 50% reduced comparing with baseline [1, 2].

The results of the analysis have shown that sites with lower blood flow and shear stress values were correlated with the sites of plaque accumulation and progression. The presented study has shown potential benefit for the prediction of disease progression.

Figure 1: Velocity distribution vector field and shear stress distribution for the baseline (a) and follow up (b).

References

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